

PRESS RELEASE

Innovative EDUbox series for the 2024 European Elections unveiled

With the June 2024 European elections approaching, educators are preparing to equip young people, especially newly enfranchised young voters between 16 and 18, with the knowledge and skills they need to engage in the democratic process. Responding to this crucial need, the EDUmake project introduces the EDUbox Politics series, offering educational resources that explore Politics, Persuasion, and Ideology.

EDUbox is an educational format developed by the Flemish national broadcaster (VRT). This free learning resource introduces secondary school students to diverse social topics and aims to inspire active participation. It is based on the theory of deep learning and blends technology, didactics, and storytelling to create an interactive and fun learning journey.

Unveiling the EDUbox Trio

EDUbox Politics: From Vote to Policy

EDUbox Politics provides young people with an understanding of decision-making processes, exploring methods to advocate for ideas and translate them into policies.

EDUbox Persuasion: About slogans, political communication & propaganda

Exploring rhetoric and persuasion techniques, students develop critical thinking skills essential for navigating modern politics.

EDUbox Ideology: Thinking about ideals and political visions

This EDUbox delves into diverse ideals shaping our worldview, emphasising their potential for both harmony and conflict, mirroring political dynamics. Through immersive role-play in the EDUbox Ideology, students investigate strategies for reconciling differing ideals and fostering cohesion in society despite divergent perspectives.

As the road to the 2024 European elections unfolds, educators are invited to use these free learning resources empowering young voters with vital knowledge for active participation in shaping their future. EDUbox Politics is currently available in English, Dutch (tailored for the Belgian context), Dutch (adapted for the audience in the Netherlands) and Croatian.

For additional information about these EDUboxes and how to access them, please visit media-and-learning.eu/project/edumake. If you're interested in customising EDUboxes for your country, you can complete the form on the webpage or reach out to Tim van Lier (Tim.VANLIER@VRT.BE) for further details.

EDUmake consortium: VRT (national public-service broadcaster for the Flemish Community of Belgium), NTR (Dutch public broadcaster), imec (R&D and innovation hub in Belgium), **University of Zagreb** (Croatia) and **Media & Learning Association**.

